

ORGANIZING THE PROCESS OF SELF-PERSONALIZATION OF STUDENTS BY STRENGTHENING MOTIVATION IN ORGANIZING INDEPENDENT EDUCATION.

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Abstract: Bugungi kunda yuzaga keladigan turli xildagi muammolar va mustaqil ta'lim olishni tashkil etishning turli xildagi usullarini yaratish borasida turli xildagi qo'shimcha taklif va mulohazalar kiritilgan. Oliy ta'lim muassasalaridagi talabalarning o'z ustida ishlashi, kelajakda o'zining sohasi bo'yicha yetuk kadr bo'lib yetishi uchun, turli xildagi hayotiy muammolardan chiqib ketish uchun mustaqil ta'limning o'rni benihoyat katta.

Keywords: motivatsiya, kasbiy mahorat, ijodiy fikrlash, qiziqish

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Abstract: Работа студентов в высших учебных заведениях самостоятельно, в дальнейшем, с различными дополнительными предложениями и соображениями по поводу создания различных методов организации самостоятельного обучения и различных проблем, возникающих сегодня. Роль самостоятельного обучения чрезвычайно важна в чтобы стать зрелым персоналом, чтобы выбраться из различных жизненных проблем.

Keywords: мотивация, профессиональные качества, творческое мышление, интерес

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Abstract: The work of students in higher education institutions on their own, in the future with various additional proposals and creation of various methods of organizing independent education and various problems that arise today. The role of independent education is extremely important in order to become a mature staff in order to get out of various life problems.

Keywords: motivation, professional skills, creative thinking, internet.

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Today, all the prerequisites have been established for the citizens of our nation to live decent lives, receive education, find employment that meets global standards, find their position in society, and engage in creative endeavors. The foundation of it is raising and educating a healthy generation. It is now necessary to create new educational models, add to and modify state educational standards, update instructional manuals, work on new projects, implement new policies, and use new and innovative methods in preschool settings and school settings.

Also, autonomous education has a huge impact on how creatively capable students in HEIs today are. Due to the fact that independent education allows

students to work independently in their profession and realize a variety of fresh concepts, imaginative ideas, and entrepreneurial endeavors.

Independent learning is learning that is done on one's own, building on the knowledge acquired through lectures and practical exercises. This approach demonstrates how students frame scientific issues, locate scientific and useful solutions, and produce a particular outcome. Students who pursue independent education are more equipped to succeed in the workplace. Self-directed learning enables students to put what they've learned in class into practice and decide for themselves about music without the guidance of a teacher. The correct formation of independent education creates an opportunity to master any educational subject, in some sense encourages the student to acquire knowledge, skills, and qualifications, and increases motivation.

If we consider the nations of the world, they engage in extensive amounts of independent study and attend classes online. They operate independently because of this. They develop fresh concepts and put them into action. We bolster the knowledge we learned in independent education with lectures and practical lessons. The resources offered by teachers or the Internet are used by students to do independent study.

Therefore, in higher education institutions, it is necessary to increase the share of independent study hours, independent education of students, analysis of critical and creative thinking systems, formation of entrepreneurial skills in students, creation of methodologies and technologies aimed at strengthening the educational process, in this regard One of the main tasks of today is the widespread introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies, educational programs and educational materials into the educational process based on international educational standards.

Formation, development, socialization, and the development of the person's capacity for independent, critical, and creative thought in the context of contemporary life are all integral parts of creating the conditions for the educational process. High-caliber professionals must be trained in accordance with the needs of the period, and students must be taught how to independently acquire knowledge and use it in the subjects of their choice.

The subjects covered in independent study include those from lectures and seminars. Theoretical knowledge, autonomous learning, creative thinking, and critical, entrepreneurial actions are all strengthened through independent education. And aids in developing a global perspective. Students develop the competencies and skills necessary for self-sufficient mastery of the fundamentals of science. Students' cognitive activity, independent creative work skills and creative

thinking skills are formed. Students develop a number of skills to develop and improve their profession.

The subjects of independent education consist of topics of lectures and seminars that students study independently. Independent education helps to strengthen students' theoretical knowledge, students themselves learn independently, think creatively and form a general Outlook. Competences and skills for independent mastering of the basics of science are formed in students cognitive activity, independent creative work skills and creative thinking skills are formed students. A number of skills are formed in students to improve and develop their profession.

Conclusion:

Students' interests and needs grow as a result of independent education. Students develop their skills and capacities through individual educational activities. Students who pursue independent education are better prepared to grow into mature professionals in their fields in the future. to boost pupils' desire for and interest in autonomous work. Achieving skills and abilities of students in independent educational activities. Timely help students in eliminating the shortcomings of their independent work. It is necessary for students to develop the necessary methodological materials for organizing independent work.

REFERENCES:

1. [HTTPS://t.me/ares.uz](https://t.me/ares.uz)
2. Academic Research in Education Sciences.
3. [w.w.w.geogle.uz](http://www.geogle.uz).
4. Science and Education.
5. Spatial deictic tense and evidentials in Korean. Natural Language Semantika. 15(3) pp.
6. Comrie B. 1976.Aspect.Cambridge University Press. Comrie B. 1985.